

ISic2732

I.Sicily inscription 2732

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building; honorific
(?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG6530 + SG7485

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333219

1. [— —]σκλο [— —]

2. [— — — — —]

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644832

EDCS 64400337

PHI 333219

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 45.1397

Nenci, G. 1995. Iscrizioni greche e latine. *Annali della scuola normale superiore di Pisa*. ser.3, vol.25: 1182-1187. At 1183 no.6

Ampolo, Carmine, Erdas, Donatella 2019. *Inscriptiones Segestanae*. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Segesta. Pisa. At G15e

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